

Participative simulation game "Foster Forest"

Introduction

Consultation between the various stakeholders in the five areas of Normandy that have signed a Territorial Forest Charter (CFT) has highlighted the need for coordinated action between stakeholders, as well as the need to explain what is being done in the forest. The aim of EUROFORNORM was therefore to create and run a regional network of forest areas in Normandy. "The future of Normandy's forests in the face of climate change" emerged as one of the priority themes.

Presentation of the role-playing game

Foster Forest is a role-playing game, a prospective and participative simulation workshop on the evolution of the forest in the face of climate change. It was born in 2015 from the realisation that, in the face of future social, economic and climatic uncertainties, forestry research needed to involve foresters in its work. Prospective workshops would enable a cross-disciplinary approach to be taken, bringing together the visions of environmental, ecological and social sciences, based on modelling approaches.

It was developed as part of his thesis by Mr Timothée FOUQUERAY (PhD student in the Ecology, Systematics and Evolution laboratory at UMR CNRS/UPS/AgroParisTech 8079).

The "game" consists of taking forest management initiatives in a climate change context and being confronted with simulation results a few decades later. This indoor workshop is led by a facilitator.

Using a digital platform, each player is given objectives and possible actions and can carry out forestry management activities (regeneration, maintenance or harvesting, as well as hunting, monitoring water quality or biodiversity, certification and/or sales, etc.).

Each session includes 5 players whose roles are set out below:

- A public forest manager from the French National Forestry Office (ONF), who may be a territorial unit manager, an agent in the forestry department, a planner or a forestry technician ;
- Two representatives of the private forest, who may be an owner, a manager or an employee of the National Centre for Forest Ownership (CNPF) ;

- One representative of the "environment", who could be an agent from a Regional Nature Park, a conservatory, etc ;
- A representative of the elected representatives, who may or may not be a forest-owning local authority, a land-use planner, a regional union of forest communities, etc.

After each session, a debriefing is held in two stages, with a round-table discussion of the strategies implemented by the participants in relation to the game, as well as free discussion of the elements that they could re-use in real life, the limits and the various contributions of the exercise. Each player can come up with alternatives and suggest changes to the scenarios.

Lessons learned

The actions undertaken have encouraged the sharing of knowledge and a better understanding of the positions and expectations of the various forestry stakeholders. Players highlighted the need to listen to each other and understand the different points of view.

Foster Forest tool proved its worth, with very positive feedback from participants. The debriefings highlighted the strengths such as awareness-raising among the players involved through a diversity of specialisations and positions. The discussions enable the perception of the objectives and criteria of the other players and the relevant choices to be made were debated in the context of climate change. Desires to pool technical and financial resources and to build local governance between the public and private sectors emerged.

The game puts the players in a situation of uncertainty, which will become increasingly frequent as a result of climate change. Finally, the workshop provided an opportunity for players to discuss issues relating to biodiversity and climate change mitigation.

*Figure 1. Presentation of a role playing session of Foster Forest with an animator, using his laptop along with a video projector to animate the session and several participants.
@fosterforest*

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/projects/euro-fornorm-14-50-61-emergence-and-animation-innovative-and-operational-network-normandv_en

--	---	---	--